

Political Parties Fascinate the Public through Social Media on Formulation and Restoration of Provinces in South Punjab, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Political Parties, Social Media, Public Affiliation, Southern Punjab and Bahawalpur province</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5573202</p>	<p><i>World is frequently switching into new form of media which is called social media. In this modern world and advancement in technology every field of life is becoming digital, social media is economical and easily accessible form of media that is having the different attributes and features to apprehensible its users. In this modern world different organizations used it to acquire their aims like as trade, business, products advertisement, culture promotion, educational, medical, health awareness and so on. Current study focused on the effects of social media on political attachment in Punjab Pakistan, survey based study was carried, population of study area was all districts of Punjab and purposive sampling techniques was used, 1000 social media users were selected without gender discrimination from Punjab, likert scale based tool was used for data collection and SPSS was used to interpret and analyze the collected data, objectives of the study were (Social media is an influential tool to change political behavior among the media forms, Political parties entrap public on formulation of southern Punjab province and restoration of Bahawalpur province, Political parties trapped the voters through social media to cast their vote, Social media is useful tool to criticize government projects and policies. Moreover, public is more verbal in political issue due to social media, Social media change preexisting public opinion about political parties), Social media became the essential tool for political parties to attract the public. Furthermore, public is also significantly adopting this new media in politics so political parties efficiently delivered their manifesto, projects and attractive planning to serve the public.</i></p>

Introduction

The popularity of social media erupted new debates for research scholars. Currently it is a source of information for masses by providing them a facility to engage the public in the political process (DelliCarpini, 2000). Smith and Rainie (2008) explore that the Internet is an important source of political information for young adults. Social networking sites provide a unique platform for sharing information. Digital media, social media or web-based services provide users and opportunity to build a public or semi-public profile (Ellison, 2007). Additionally, social media is strongly linked to political activities which include mobilization of public on different issues, such as social, political and religious (Wilson and Dunn, 2011). Social media has different forms of interaction between voters and politicians and the content created by the user can provide meaningful information that citizens could not access otherwise. The collaborative and open nature of digital media can reduce barriers for the people to enter into the politics, especially for un-privileged political groups (Kushin and Yamamoto, 2010). Thus, social media can have a significant impact on the political arena. (Effing, van Hillegersberg and Huibers 2011) presented a survey of the Dutch House of Representatives on 9 June 2010 found that politicians with maximum use of social media attract more voters, with a positive correlation among all political parties. Social media is an essential part in this digital age.

Social media has become an integral part of everyone's daily routine. Due to the advancement in digital media and internet connectivity the world has become a global village today rightly predicted decades ago. This connectivity not only brought awareness in public but also provided some challenges and opportunities to the users (Briones, Kuch, Liu and Jin, 2011). Effects of social media on society are increasing day by day. Social media effected many spheres of life (Shirky, 2011).

This study focused on the effects of social media on public and political parties, so the major goal was to find out how social media has affected political view of public in Punjab Pakistan. Social media is playing a crucial role in promoting democracy in Pakistan. It provides quick access to users especially related to elections and emerging election trends. All parties compete to use social media more effectively and influence maximum users. Public has switched from conventional media to digital media and they use social media platforms for updates especially related to political developments. Social media users express their view freely and easily considering

it users friendly (Stieglitz and Dang-Xuan, 2013). Schlozman, Verba, and Brady (2012) elaborate that arrival of social media has entirely changed the traditional political scenario. Smith, Gill, Lunt, and Brooks (2009) maintained the arrival of digital media draw the attention of research scholars to the increasing contribution of youngster in politics. Cohen and Cohen (2012) explored that youngster showed their interest about political issues and also contributed in politics by setting up political groups to promote their parties or leaders and share information instantly among public groups. Political parties already have very strong social media wings to influence voters (Lampos, Preotiuc-Pietro, and Cohn, 2013). Facebook, Twitter, MySpace, blogs and YouTube are important social sharing sites and these all forms of digital media.

- Facebook
- YouTube
- Twitter
- WhatsApp

Social media permits its users, groups and political parties to share their point of view, their opinion, and share their experiences in a more interactive and coherent way. The fame of the digital media is growing quickly, creating new social networking sites. Recently, reported that number of daily active users of Facebook are 1.9 worldwide and roughly it is estimated that 2.89 users actively used Facebook monthly, in the Pakistan are 45 million people are active Facebook users (The Statistics Portal for Market Data, 2021). Twitter has more than 199 million users worldwide in 2021 (Marketing Agencies New York, 2021). Social media communication cannot be measured as a linear connection, just like radio, television and newspapers, because it facilitates two-way communication (McClurg and Holbrook, 2009). Social media has changed Facebook and Twitter and MySpace campaigns in many ways. Social media allows politicians to converse straight to the voters, which helps them organize their campaigns and at the same time get immediate feedback. Social media is growing rapidly in Pakistan. Millions of people have accounts on social media sites such as twitter and Facebook. Social networking sites are not limited to Pakistan, but also allow young Pakistanis to connect with young people around the world and keep in touch with members from other countries. In Pakistan political parties manipulate the social issue among public and trap them to gain their interest especially during election campaign for this purpose all political parties utilize different form of social media.

Significance of the Study

This study focuses on the importance of social media for political parties to disseminate their messages to the voters effectively. On the other voters also use social media to get awareness about different political parties and their manifestos. In 2018 elections political parties offered many development packages including the creation of news province in South Punjab. Keeping in view the increased focus for this region the study focuses on finding out the relation between the pledging of new province, use of social media and changing voting behaviors.

Rationale of the Study

The study aims to investigate the effects of social media on political affiliations in Punjab Pakistan. Findings of this study will be beneficial for communication experts especially in the context of next general elections in Pakistan. This study also determines which political party used social media more effectively. It sheds light on changing political affiliations after having exposure to different political campaigns on social media. It provides guidelines to major political parties in Pakistan about the popular trends among voters especially in connection of social media which greatly influences voting behavior and change public opinion.

Objectives of the Study

1. Social media is influential tool to change political behavior among the media forms
2. Political parties entrap the public on formulation of southern Punjab province and restoration of Bahawalpur province
3. Political parties trap the voters utilizing social media to cast their vote
4. Social media is useful tool to criticize government projects and policies
5. Public is more verbal in political issue due to social media
6. Social media change pre-existing public opinion about political parties

Methodology

This study adopted survey methodology to collect data. Population was social media active users. The researcher used point 5 likert scale questionnaire as a tool for data collection. Universe of the study included social media users from colleges, universities, public and private organization's officials including male and female belonging to Punjab Pakistan. The researcher intentionally selected those respondents who were more active on social media. To meet the requirement of this study, the researchers adopted non-probability sampling method. The sampling technique was based on purposive sampling technique. The sample size of the study was 1000 respondents, out of which properly answered response count was 927 and rate of feedback was 92.7 percent.

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the participant's sample of the study

Demographic Characteristics		<i>f</i>	%
Status	Employee	257	27.7%
	Non-Employee	670	72.3%
Qualification	Matric	68	7.3%
	F.A/F.Sc	248	26.8%
	B.A/B.Sc	280	30.2%
	M.A/M.Sc	185	20.0%
	MS/ M.Phil	115	12.4%
	PhD	31	3.3%
Gender	Male	565	60.9%
	Female	362	39.1%
Residence	Urban	581	62.7%
	Rural	346	37.3%
Age	15-25 Years	758	81.8%
	26-35 years	136	14.7%
	36-45 years	28	3.0%
	Above 45 years	5	.5%

Table 1 as described the sample of the participants was taken from Punjab province and a total of 1000 were taken, Demographics of respondents include Punjab Province to whom they belong as data was collected from 36 districts of Punjab Pakistan and 927 respondents response to data collection out of 1000 were sampled. As a sample and among those 27.7% were employee and 72.3% were not employee. Qualification of respondents background Matric 7.3% Intermediate 26.8% Graduation 30.2%, Master 20%, M.Phil 12.4%, and PhD 3.3%. As a sample and among those 1000 participants 60.9% were male and 39.1% were females. Respondent's background 37.3% rural and urban were 62.7%, gender male 60.9% and 39.1% female, age of the response 15-25 years 81.8%, 26-35 were 14.7%, 36-45 were 3.0%, to above 45 years .5% respondents all over the Punjab.

Table 2: Public is interested in political issues in Pakistan due to social media.

Option	Frequency	Percent
Yes	608	65.6%
No	319	34.4%
Total	927	100.0%

Table 2 the respondents of social media users answered about public is interested in political issues in Pakistan due to social media, the majority show their interest and also graphically described their interest about politics that shows the majority users of social media 600 plus out of 927 of users of social media taking interest about political issues and politics, this is significance for social media effects on politics in Punjab Pakistan.

Table 2: Social was useful tool for General election 2008 to 2018 in Pakistan.

Option	Frequency	Percent
2008	76	8.2%
2013	152	16.4%
2018	699	75.4%
Total	927	100.0%

Table 3 social media was useful tool for general election campaign in Pakistan the majority respondents answered that in general Election 2018 was top of the priority to utilized for election campaign 75 percent respondents agreed that in election campaign 2018 social media was more effective rather than previous general election in Pakistan.

Table 3: Your favorite political party

Option	Frequency	Percent
PPP	57	6.1%
PTI	460	49.6%
PML-N	224	24.2%
PMLQ	32	3.5%
Jamat-e- Islami	24	2.6%
JUI	20	2.2%
Any other political party	110	11.9%
Total	927	100.0%

Table 4 respondents show their favorite political party as a Pakistan Tehrik e Insaf 460 respondent and second one was Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz were 224 respondents showed their favorite political party in Punjab this finding show the public affiliation is with Pakistan Tehrik e Insaf.

Table 4: Political party attracts the voters on political slogans by using social media

Option	Frequency	Percent
PPP	117	12.6%
PTI	633	68.3%
PML-N	134	14.5%
PMLQ	20	2.2%
Jamat E Islami	23	2.5%
Total	927	100.0%

Table 5 political parties attract the voters in election campaign on social media by utilizing political slogan in this matter Pakistan Tehrik e Insaf created slogan that was much liked and attract the public on social media at second one attractive political slogan was Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz and third one was Pakistan People's Party slogan was famous among peoples at Punjab.

Table 5: Your favorite form of social media for political awareness

Option	Frequency	Percent
Facebook	387	41.7%
WhatsApp	183	19.7%
Twitter	195	21.0%
YouTube	110	11.9%
My Space	9	1.0%
Any other form of Social Media	43	4.6%
Total	927	100.0%

Table 6 respondent's favorite form of social media was Facebook which show 42 percent response and second form selected as a favorite that was twitter 21 percent and third one was WhatsApp 20 percent social media users select it as a favorite, number four was YouTube, 5 percent users were others form of social media in Punjab but only one percent users were select MySpace as favorite social media form that shows MySpace was not utilized by public and political parties as a political campaign tool in Punjab.

Table 6: Fake and anti-political post and links on Social Media create hatred among peoples of different parties

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	294	31.7	3.89	1.112
Agree	424	45.7		
Undecided	120	12.9		
Disagree	69	7.5		
Strongly Disagree	20	2.2		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 7 explores the opinion of participants about the statement "Fake and anti-political post and links on Social Media create hatred among peoples of different parties". Data shows that, 45.7% of respondents are agreed that fake and anti-political post and links on social media create hatred among peoples of different parties, whereas 31.7% were strongly agreed, 7.5% disagreed, 2.2% strongly disagreed and 12.9% of respondents were undecided to the statement. Majority of 77.4% of respondents are agreed and 9.7% disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 1.112$) shows positive response with the statement that fake and anti-political post and links on social media create hatred among peoples of different parties.

Table 7: Fake Political post on Social Media deteriorate the ethics among people

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	264	28.5	3.86	1.005
Agree	393	42.4		
Undecided	177	19.1		
Disagree	65	7.0		
Strongly Disagree	28	3.0		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 8 explores the opinion of participants about the statement "Fake Political post on Social Media deteriorate the ethics among people". Data shows that, 42.4% of respondents are agreed that fake political post on social

media deteriorate the ethics among people, whereas 28.5% are strongly agreed, 7.0% disagreed, 3% strongly disagreed and 19.1% of respondents are undecided to the statement. Majority of 70.9% of respondents are agreed and 10% disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 1.005$) shows positive response with the statement that fake political post on social media deteriorate the ethics among people.

Table 8: Social media is a source of knowledge and information about politics.

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	281	30.3	3.87	1.034
Agree	372	40.1		
Undecided	175	18.9		
Disagree	68	7.3		
Strongly Disagree	31	3.3		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 9 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Social media is a source of knowledge and information about politics”. Data shows that, 30.3% of respondents are strongly agreed that Social media is a source of knowledge and information about politics, whereas 40.1 % are agreed, 18.9 % undecided, 7.3% disagreed and 3.3 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 70.4% of respondents are agreed and 10.6 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.87$, $SD = 1.034$) shows positive response with the statement that social media is a source of knowledge and information about politics

Table 9: Social media is accessible for general public.

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	243	26.2	3.77	1.057
Agree	384	41.4		
Undecided	176	19.0		
Disagree	90	9.7		
Strongly Disagree	34	3.7		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 10 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Social media is accessible for general public”. Data shows that, 26.2 % of respondents are strongly agreed that Social media is accessible for general public, whereas 41.4 % are agreed, 19.0 % undecided, 9.7 % disagreed and 3.7 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 67.6% of respondents are agreed and 13.4 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 1.057$) shows positive response with the statement that Social media is accessible for general public.

Table 10: Social media is powerful tool to highlighting the creation of southern Punjab Province among public of southern Punjab.

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	201	21.7	3.62	1.074
Agree	352	38.0		
Undecided	231	24.9		
Disagree	103	11.1		
Strongly Disagree	40	4.3		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 11 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Social media is powerful tool to highlighting the creation of southern Punjab Province among public of southern Punjab”. Data shows that, 21.7% of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 38.0 % are agreed, 24.9 % undecided, 11.1 disagreed and 4.3 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 59.7% of respondents are agreed and 15.4 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 1.074$) shows positive response with the statement that Social media is powerful tool to highlighting the creation of southern Punjab Province among public of southern Punjab.

Table 11: PTI attracts the voters on formulation of southern Punjab province during election campaign 2018 on social media.

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	255	27.5	3.76	1.100
Agree	372	40.1		
Undecided	160	17.3		
Disagree	100	10.8		
Strongly Disagree	40	4.3		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 12 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “PTI attracts the voters on formulation of southern Punjab province during election campaign 2018 on social media”. Data shows that, 27.5% of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 40.1 % are agreed, 17.3 % undecided, 10.8 % disagreed and 4.3 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 67.6% of respondents are agreed and 15.1 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 1.100$) shows positive response with the statement PTI attracts the voters on formulation of southern Punjab province during election campaign 2018 on social media.

Table 12: Political issues discussion on Social Media affects the voter’s opinion on local body elections in Pakistan.

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	219	23.6	3.66	1.084
Agree	354	38.2		
Undecided	217	23.4		
Disagree	95	10.2		
Strongly Disagree	42	4.5		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 13 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Political issues discussion on Social Media affects the voter’s opinion on local body elections in Pakistan. Data shows that, 23.6% of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 38.2 % are agreed, 23.4 % undecided, 10.2 % disagreed and 4.5 % of respondents are disagreed to the statement. Majority of 61.8 % of respondents are agreed and 14.7 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.66$, $SD = 1.084$) shows positive response with the statement that Political issues discussion on Social Media affects the voter’s opinion on local body elections in Pakistan.

Table 13: Social Media is useful tool of political parties for election campaign

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	250	27.0	3.84	1.007
Agree	407	43.9		
Undecided	176	19.0		
Disagree	62	6.7		
Strongly Disagree	32	3.5		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 14 explores the opinion of participants about the statement Social Media is useful tool of political parties for election campaign. Data shows that, 27.0 % of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 43 % are agreed, 19.0 % undecided, 6.7 % disagreed and 3.5 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 70.9% of respondents are agreed and 10.1 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 1.007$) shows positive response with the statement that Social Media is useful tool of political parties for election campaign.

Table 14: Government attracts the voters to supported formulation of southern Punjab province on social media

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	212	22.9	3.61	1.120
Agree	344	37.1		
Undecided	232	25.0		
Disagree	79	8.5		
Strongly Disagree	60	6.5		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 15 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “PTI Government attracts the voters to supported formulation of southern Punjab province on social media, Data shows that, 22.9 % of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 37.1% are agreed, 25% undecided, 8.5 % disagreed and 6.5 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 60.0% of respondents are agreed and 15.0 % disagreed, the

mean score is ($M = 3.61$, $SD = 1.120$) shows positive response with the statement that PTI Government attracts the voters to supported formulation of southern Punjab province on social media

Table 15: Public of Bahawalpur raise their voice on social media to restore Bahawalpur province

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	207	22.3	3.55	1.114
Agree	298	32.1		
Undecided	279	30.1		
Disagree	88	9.5		
Strongly Disagree	55	5.9		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 16 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Public of Bahawalpur raise their voice on social media to restore Bahawalpur province”. Data shows that, 22.3 % of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 32.1 % are agreed, 30.1% undecided, 9.5% disagreed and 5.9 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 54.4 % of respondents are agreed and 15.4% disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 1.114$) shows positive response with the statement that Public of Bahawalpur raise their voice on social media to restore Bahawalpur province.

Table 16: Social Media users in Pakistan need ethical maturity to support their opinion about political parties

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	352	38.0	3.92	1.155
Agree	322	34.7		
Undecided	136	14.7		
Disagree	60	6.5		
Strongly Disagree	57	6.1		
Total	927	100.0		

Table 17 explores the opinion of participants about the statement “Social Media users in Pakistan need ethical maturity to support their opinion about political parties. Data shows that, 38.0 % of respondents are strongly agreed, whereas 34.7 % are agreed, 14.7 % undecided, 6.5 % disagreed and 6.1 % of respondents are strongly disagreed to the statement. Majority of 72.7% of respondents are agreed and 12.6 % disagreed, the mean score is ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 1.155$) shows positive response with the statement that Social Media users in Pakistan need ethical maturity to support their opinion about political parties

Table 17: Gender base effects of social media on political affiliation

Factors	Gender	M	SD	t	p	95% CI
Southern Punjab, Bahawalpur Province	Male	14.43	3.097	-1.36	.17	[-.660, .119]
	Female	14.70	2.784			
Political Affiliation	Male	30.05	4.675	-2.77	.00	[-1.453, -.250]
	Female	30.90	4.433			
Role of Social Media	Male	46.14	6.456	-1.12	.26	[-1.274, .346]
	Female	46.61	5.756			
Effects of Social Media	Male	45.79	5.877	-2.52	.01	[-1.759, -.219]
	Female	46.78	5.885			

Table 18 presents results about gender wise analysis of data about participants’ response about the Southern Punjab and restoration of Bahawalpur Province. Mean score of female participants (mean = 14.70, standard deviation = 2.784) is higher than male participants (mean = 14.43, standard deviation = 3.097). T-test indicates insignificant mean difference ($t = -1.36$, $p = .17$). Investigate that women participants had better opinion about the formulation of Southern Punjab and restoration of Bahawalpur Province rather than male participant. Mean score of female participants (mean = 30.90, standard deviation = 4.433) is higher than male participants (mean = 30.05, standard deviation = 4.675). T-test indicates significant mean difference ($t = -2.77$, $p = 0.000$). Investigate that women participants had better opinion about the political affiliation. Mean score of female participants (mean = 46.61, standard deviation = 5.756) is higher than male participants (mean = 46.14, standard deviation = 6.456). T-test indicates insignificant mean difference ($t = -1.12$, $p = .26$). Investigate that women participants had better opinion about the role of social media. Mean score of female participants (mean = 46.78, standard deviation = 5.885) is higher than male participants (mean = 45.79, standard deviation = 5.877). T-test indicates significant mean difference ($t = -2.52$, $p = 0.001$). This explores that female participants had better opinion about the effects of social media.

Table 18: Effects of status wise use of social media and political affiliation

Factors	Status	M	SD	t	p	95% CI
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Southern Punjab ,Bahawalpur Province	Employee	14.39	3.027	-.847	.397	[-.649, .258]
	Non-employee	14.58	2.974			
	Non-employee	30.57	4.531			
Role of Social Media	Employee	46.28	6.513	-.137	.891	[-1.005, .874]
	Non-employee	46.35	6.079			
Effects of Social Media	Employee	45.85	5.403	1.009	.313	[-1.354, .434]
	Non-employee	46.31	6.033			

Table 19, presents results about employee and non-employee's analysis of data about participants' response about formulation of Southern Punjab and restoration of Bahawalpur Province. Mean score of employee participants (mean = 14.39, standard deviation = 3.027) is higher than nonemployee participants (mean = 14.58, standard deviation = 2.974). T-test indicates insignificant mean difference (t = -.847, p = .397). This explores that employee participants had better opinion about the formulation of Southern Punjab and restoration of Bahawalpur province rather than non-employees. Mean score of employee participants (mean = 46.28, standard deviation = 6.653) is higher than nonemployee participants (mean = 46.35, standard deviation = 6.079). T-test indicates significant mean difference (t = -.137, p = 0.891). Investigate that employee participants had better opinion about the role of social media. Mean score of employee participants (mean = 45.85, standard deviation = 5.403) is higher than non-employee participants (mean = 46.31, standard deviation = 6.033). T-test indicates insignificant mean difference (t = -1.009, p = .313). Investigate that employee participants had better opinion about the effects of social media.

Finding Discussion

This study highlights social media effects of political affiliation in Pakistan that how political parties, public and politicians utilized it to disseminate information (Michaelsen, 2011), advancement in technology and social networks sites have an impact on political communication in both developed and under developing countries, although developed countries practice larger impact because of explosion of the Internet (Riaz, 2010). Digital media has significant effects on the social and political learning of citizens, especially youth (Khan and Shahbaz, 2015). A recent study revealed that digital media have powerful political influence on individuals in Pakistan ((Karamat and Farooq, 2016). People actively use new media for political information such as sharing opinions and discussing issues around politics with fellow community members (Arshad and Hassan, 2014). In Pakistan, Facebook is the most used network among youth for political information compared with other social networks such as Twitter. According to the recent study, Pakistan has the second highest population of youth which has created huge impact on the dynamics of Pakistan's politics ((Ittefaq and Iqbal, 2018). Since 2008 political parties of Pakistan are actively using social media and it has changed the dynamics of politics in Pakistan (Eijaz, 2013).

Social media influences masses in Pakistan that's why political parties use it extensively to run their election campaigns. In 2018 general elections PTI won more seats which involved many factors including effective use of social media where they masterly propagated their agenda of creation of new province for the people of southern Punjab and residents of Bahawalpur. All the political parties were involved in massive propaganda against each other at social media platforms. The winning party PTI projected a better manifesto by offering a separate province for the Siraiki people.

Conclusion

Social media is effective and essential for public and political parties in Pakistan. It provides greater outreach to project the government plans and services for public. Being an interactive media it gives masses a chance to make government accountable in context of its performance and governance. Today effective political campaigns mainly target social media users and it is the social media which set agenda of conventional media.

Limitations

This study was limited to the manipulation of voters' pre-existing opinion with the help of social media. It did not focus on the greater political awareness with the help of social media.

Recommendations

Social media regulations should be implanted in Pakistan to ensure some practices of following ethics and standards especially related to news media. Legislating required halting bombardment of fake news stories and irresponsible media content. Indecent language and character assignment should not be allowed even in election campaigns.

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